

21NRM05 STASIS

D3: Report on the development of open-source reference hardware (RF coil, exciter, modulators, RF power amplifiers) and open-source control software, including traceable measurement procedures that allow testing of implant under parallel transmission (pTx) MR conditions

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:
German Cancer Research Centre (DKFZ)

Due date of the deliverable: 30th of September 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30th of September 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

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Glossary

B_1^+	Circularly polarized flux density, transmit field
DAC	Digital-to-analogue converter
FPGA	Field programmable gate array
GUI	Graphical user interface
IQ-Modulator	Inphase/quadrature modulator
LDMOS	Laterally diffused metal-oxide-semiconductor
MR	Magnetic resonance
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
RF	Radio frequency
RMS	Root mean square
ϵ_r	Relative permittivity
σ	Conductivity

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1 Summary

This report provides an overview of the hardware and software components of the STASIS open-source exposure system. The various parts of the system are briefly described. As the system is open source, detailed information is available in the corresponding repositories. Photographs of the RF coil array and the transmit chain are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The 8-channel transmit array (left) and the control system and amplifiers in a 19" rack (right).

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose

The STASIS RF exposure system is an open-source hardware and software platform designed for implant testing under exposure to radiofrequency (RF) fields, such as those encountered in the environment of an MRI system. For this purpose, the target RF frequency is 128 MHz, corresponding to the resonant frequency of protons in a 3 Tesla magnetic field. The system is capable of transmitting on eight independent RF channels, enabling parallel transmission.

To ensure the design is easily accessible to potential users, all design files and software are publicly available and can be accessed via the following repositories:

https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Exposure_Hardware

https://github.com/sOrzada/STASIS_Control

All hardware components of the exposure system are licensed under the CERN-OHL-W while the software is licensed under a GNU GPL v3. In addition, the project has been submitted to the conformity assessment body of the Open Source Imaging Initiative e.V. (<https://www.opensourceimaging.org>) to assess its open-source status according to DIN SPEC 3105.

To further improve accessibility, standard components with long production lifespans were selected wherever possible. For example, standard logic components were used instead of specialised microcontrollers or FPGAs.

2.2 System Overview

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the STASIS exposure system.

The STASIS exposure system consists of 4 main parts as shown in Figure 2. The user interacts with the system via a graphical user interface (GUI), from which the control hardware can be programmed. The control system manages timing and generates eight independent RF signals, which are transmitted to eight separate RF amplifiers. These amplifiers then deliver high-peak and average power signals to the antenna array, creating the RF fields to which the object under test is exposed.

The antenna array is an eight-channel microstrip line array with an inner diameter of 59.5 cm, matching the size of a standard clinical MRI system bore. A more detailed description is provided in Section 3.

The RF generation system comprises all electronics required to drive the RF chain in a manner that simulates an MRI environment. It handles transmission timing and pseudo-reception (pauses), generates the RF centre frequency, and modulates the baseband signals onto the centre frequency for all eight channels. Further details can be found in Section 4.

The RF amplifiers are solid-state power amplifiers capable of peak output powers exceeding 1 kW. They are also capable of continuous wave (CW) transmission at lower root mean square (RMS) power levels. These amplifiers operate as stand-alone units and can potentially be used independently of the STASIS system. A detailed description is given in Section 5.

To provide a user-friendly operating experience, custom software with an intuitive graphical user interface was developed. To ensure maintainability, the software is written in Python and follows an object-oriented design. The GUI allows full system configuration and all required calibrations, such as gradient linearization. A full description of the software is provided in Section 6.

3 RF array

3.1 Introduction

The RF array is designed to resemble an eight-channel transmit array of a size and type suitable for use within a 3 Tesla MRI system. Its design is closely based on the configuration proposed by Vernickel et al. (1) in 2007. The array consists of eight microstrip antenna elements, each electrically connected to its adjacent neighbours. A photograph of the RF array mounted on its trolley is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Photo of the 8-channel RF array.

3.2 Mechanical Design

The coil housing is constructed from poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). A schematic is shown in Figure 4. The overall length of the housing is 820 mm, comprising 800 mm cylindrical walls and 10 mm end rings on each side. The inner diameter of the housing is 594 mm, closely matching the inner diameter of a Siemens 60 cm bore (actual diameter: 595 mm).

The inner cylinder of the housing has a wall thickness of 8 mm, while the outer cylinder's wall thickness is 6 mm. The outer diameter of the housing is 700 mm, resulting in a 39 mm gap between the two cylinders, within which the antenna elements are positioned.

The inner surface of the outer cylinder is lined with adhesive copper foil, serving as the ground plane for the microstrip antennas. As the array is not intended for use in an MR environment, there is no requirement for eddy current mitigation; therefore, the copper cladding is continuous. The ground plane consists of four large sections of copper foil, joined by copper bands with electrically conductive adhesive applied across the seams.

Figure 4: Sketch of the array including the housing. The inner side of the outer cylinder is clad with copper foil. Note that the small holders for the trimmer rods are placed directly in line with the center of the micro-strip lines. For more information refer to the CAD model in the Data.

Each antenna element has a width of 100 mm and a length of 450 mm. The distance between the centre of the microstrip and the ground plane is 37.3 mm, maintained by 3D-printed mechanical holders made from PLA. The copper layer of the microstrips is located on the side of the board facing the ground plane. Consequently, the capacitors are also mounted on this side, which allows the microstrips to be positioned closer to the inner cylinder of the housing.

3.3 Electrical Design

The electrical design of the array closely follows the configuration proposed by Vernickel et al. (1). The circuit schematic of a single antenna element, including its electrical connections to adjacent elements, is shown in Figure 5. The component values indicated in the schematic represent total capacitances, inclusive of parasitic capacitances from the PCBs.

To achieve a homogeneous current distribution along the microstrip, each element is divided into five sections, interconnected by pairs of 33 pF capacitors. A 22 pF capacitor is placed at the end of the strip. To minimize coupling between adjacent elements, a decoupling network is implemented. This consists of a 560 pF capacitor connected to two coaxial cables, each 130 mm in length, for each directly adjacent element. These cables are terminated with 7.6 pF capacitors, which interface with the corresponding coaxial lines from neighbouring elements.

Simulations revealed that significant peak voltages can occur across these coupling capacitors. In the actual implementation, it is therefore necessary to replace each with multiple capacitors in series to ensure voltage handling capability and reliability.

Figure 5: Schematic showing one microstrip element with the connection to the neighboring antennas. The capacitor values given in this schematic are total capacitances. Some of the lumped elements on the actual coil have different values due to parasitic capacitances of the PCBs.

3.4 RF field simulation results

All simulations of the RF array were carried out in CST Microwave Studio (Dassault Système, France).

For the simulations the array was loaded with a homogeneous phantom with electrical properties that correspond to the mean of the human body at 128 MHz ($\epsilon_r=52$; $\sigma=0.47$ S/m).

A transverse view of the B_1^+ field distribution for the birdcage mode and a stimulated power of 1W is shown in Figure 6. It shows the pattern typical for 3T body imaging with a high intensity in the center and two lower intensity bands.

Figure 6: Simulated B_1^+ field distribution of the CP+ mode (birdcage mode) for stimulated power of 1W. The typical pattern with a high intensity center and two lower intensity bands as known from 3T body imaging is visible.

Figure 7 shows the B_1^+ for the birdcage mode and stimulated power of 8 kW on a central line on the z-axis within the phantom. The values vary between 18 μT and 22 μT . This field strength is sufficient to emulate the transmit fields of an MRI system.

Figure 7: B_1^+ for the birdcage mode and a stimulated power of 8 kW on a central line on the z-axis through the phantom. The values vary between 18 μT and 22 μT .

4 RF Generation System

4.1 Overview

The RF Generation System (Figure 8) produces both digital and analogue signals required for the operation of the RF exposure system. It emulates the signal and timing generation of an MRI system, allowing the user to configure a sequence of RF pulses and pauses that replicate an actual imaging sequence.

The system is built around IEC 60603-2 (formerly DIN 41612) connectors and housed in a Eurocard rack system (IEC 60297), facilitating modularity and ease of component exchange. For example, by adding additional racks with extra modulator cards, the number of RF channels can be easily expanded.

Figure 8: A picture of the front of the Control System.

A simplified schematic of the RF Generation System is shown in Figure 9. The Control System comprises a signal generator that provides a stable 128 MHz RF signal, a timing control module that switches between transmit and pseudo-receive modes, and modulator modules capable of adjusting the amplitude and phase of

the RF signal. Additionally, the control system includes modules for signal distribution and communication with a PC.

Figure 9: Schematic overview of the control system.

During the development of the system, care was taken to select components with long production lifetimes and good availability to ensure that this open-source system can be easily replicated. For example, only standard logic chips are used, with no FPGAs or microcontrollers included.

Communication with a PC is achieved via a USB-to-SPI converter. Both USB and SPI are industry standards.

4.2 Timing

The system timings are derived from a 10 MHz temperature-compensated crystal oscillator. A programmable clock divider reduces this clock frequency, which is then followed by two programmable counters—one for transmission and one for pseudo-reception. This arrangement enables highly precise and reproducible timing.

4.3 Modulation

The RF Modulator Module is a high-speed IQ modulator that accepts an analogue RF signal and adjusts its amplitude and phase according to values stored in its internal SRAM. Driven by a clock signal from the backplane, a programmable counter within the modulator increments the SRAM address by one on each clock cycle, retrieving a new amplitude and phase setting from memory.

The modulator can update its settings every 0.1 μs with a resolution of 14 bits for both in-phase (I) and quadrature (Q) components and can store up to 65,536 states internally. The IQ modulator chip used in the module (AD8345) operates at frequencies corresponding to MRI field strengths ranging from 3 T to 21 T and has been successfully implemented in a 32-channel transmit MRI system previously (2).

The module features one input for the centre frequency, one RF output for the modulated signal, and an output indicating the amplifier state.

5 RF power amplifiers

Figure 10: Front view of one RF amplifier.

The RF amplifier (Figure 10) is an LDMOS output-stage amplifier incorporating a circulator and power supply. It is capable of delivering pulses of up to 1.5 kW peak power (4 ms pulse length, 20% duty cycle) in high-power mode, and a continuous-wave output of up to 30 W in low-power mode.

Figure 11: Schematic overview of the RF power amplifier.

A schematic overview of the RF amplifier is shown in Figure 11. The amplifier contains its own power supplies, which accept inputs from 110 V_{AC} to 240 V_{AC}.

Amplification is achieved through three successive stages, with the final stage being a high-power LDMOS stage. The drain voltage of this stage can be switched internally between 65 V (high-power, pulsed mode) and 24 V (low-power, continuous mode). Switching between high- and low-power modes takes 1 μs. In many practical scenarios, this enables mode switching within a pulse, reducing power consumption and heat generation—particularly in pulses with a high peak-to-average power ratio.

To supply the energy required for short high-power pulses in high-power mode, a capacitor array is employed alongside a voltage regulator capable of delivering more than 40 A.

All three amplifier stages, the high-current voltage regulator, and a 50 Ω resistor for the circulator are mounted on a heat sink cooled by airflow generated by four 60 mm fans.

6 Graphical User Interface

6.1 Overview

The graphical user interface (GUI) and the software used to program the hardware of the exposure system are written in Python. Object-oriented programming was employed to make the code easily accessible and adaptable. Python was chosen due to its widespread use and ease of learning.

The GUI provides the user with tools to configure the system state, design or load pulse sequences, and perform comprehensive calibration of the entire transmit chain.

6.2 Main window

When users start the software, they are presented with the main window, shown in Figure 12.

From this window, the user can set the timings and mode of operation, navigate to other sections, view information on the current system status, and start or stop the system. Pulse options include loading NumPy or MATLAB arrays, as well as designing simple pulses using the Pulse Tool (see Section 6.3).

Figure 12: Main window of the graphical user interface.

6.3 Pulse Tool

To provide users with an intuitive way to generate realistic RF pulses, a Pulse Tool is integrated into the GUI (Figure 13). Three pulse types can be selected: sinc pulses, rectangular pulses, and random noise. For the sinc pulse, both the bandwidth and centre frequency shift can be specified, while for the rectangular pulse, the centre frequency shift can be adjusted.

For all three pulse types, peak amplitudes—and phases where applicable—can be set independently for each channel. For user convenience, both the pulse waveform and its spectrum are displayed within the GUI.

Figure 13: The Pulse Tool window.

6.4 Calibration

For precise measurements using the exposure system, it is essential to perform accurate calibration of the transmit chain. To this end, the system software includes sophisticated calibration procedures, carried out in three steps:

1. **Zero-point calibration:** This step calibrates the feed-through of the modulators. Ideally, requesting a 0 V output from the modulator ICs and digital-to-analogue converters (DACs) would produce exactly 0 V output. In reality, however, the zero point is slightly offset. Careful calibration allows this offset to be identified and corrected within the precision limits of the DACs.
2. **Amplifier linearity calibration:** In an ideal amplifier, the gain—the ratio of output power to input power—remains constant across all input power levels. In practice, however, the gain varies with input power, and the phase relationship between input and output signals also changes. By performing pointwise measurements, a correction table is generated to linearize the amplifiers by adjusting the input signals accordingly.
3. **Power level calibration:** Following the linearity calibration, a simple power-level correction is applied to account for any residual inaccuracies.

All calibration steps are performed via dedicated GUIs. For example, Figure 13 shows the GUI for amplifier linearity calibration. These interfaces include straightforward controls and explanatory images to make the calibration process quick, easy, and safe. Graphical representations of the results assist users in assessing the validity of the calibration.

Figure 14: Linearity Calibration Window.

7 Summary and Conclusion

In summary, an open-source reference hardware consisting of an 8-channel 3T pTx body coil, performant parallel transmission RF exposure hardware and operating software have been developed, which is suitable, amongst others, for offline implant testing by manufacturers or test houses.

More detailed information on the reference hardware and software can be found in the public repositories, and its application is further detailed in deliverable D1 of the STASIS project.

The aims of the STASIS project deliverable have been successfully achieved, fulfilling Objective 2 of the project.

8 References

1. Vernickel P, Roschmann P, Findekle C, Ludeke KM, Leussler C, Overweg J, Katscher U, Grasslin I, Schunemann K. Eight-channel transmit/receive body MRI coil at 3T. *Magnetic resonance in medicine : official journal of the Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine / Society of Magnetic Resonance in Medicine* 2007;58(2):381-389.
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